

ESSENTIAL APPROACHES TO TEACHING WRITING IN ESL**Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction named after****Department of Foreign Languages Mirzo Ulugbek****English language teacher****Zamira Suyarova Sheraliyevna**

Teaching and learning writing in ESL classrooms are demanding. Researchers develop various theories to assist the learners and teachers because in ESL students have to cope with language proficiency and the process of writing. Theories are crucial for the teachers to know and understand the theories in teaching writing because it will allow the teachers “to implement research-based practices better”. Writing is a thinking process. To write, a writer needs to use the mental process such as brainstorming, planning and organizing and it needs creativity. Therefore, cognitive writing process aims to teach students to use mental processing in producing a piece of writing. It is a popular than other writing theories as it has many benefits. This theory was introduced by Flower and Hayes (1981, p.366) “through observations of students’ writing and made effort to “introduce theory of cognitive processes involved in composing and to lay groundwork for more detailed study of thinking processes in writing”[1]. The four elements highlighted by Flower and Hayes in this theory are “Writers have to go through a process of thinking before writing, a higher-order organizational structure takes place during these procedures, composing involves setting objectives, and authors generate macro and micro objectives to finish the writing task (Flower & Hayes 1981, p.366). In short it focuses exclusively on the mental writing process.

Writing approaches are essential in every writing lesson. ESL teachers should determine the approach need to be applied in one particular lesson for a few reasons. Identifying the correct approach in a writing classroom is crucial to see an effective outcome. Choosing a non-ideal approach will simply make the lessons daunting to the ESL learners and cause disappointment to the teachers after so much of handwork put in the planning and teaching. In other words, it will demotivate the teachers as well as the students. Next, adapting an appropriate approach in the classroom is important depending on the goal set by the teacher. For instance, beginners with very limited proficiency should be exposed to product-based approach as they need model or examples to begin their writing journey. Without an approach, the writing classroom will move in multiple directions thus the goal set for the particular lesson will not be achievable. Hence,

writing approaches are important to meet the goals of the writing. Furthermore, implying different types of approaches, enables students exposed to various types of methods. This will give opportunity to students to identify and use the correct approach in future writing based on their writing purpose. Students who are aware of the approaches produce a quality piece of writing. Approaches to Teaching Writing in ESL Classrooms Writing approaches to first language users differs from the second language learners. Researches had formulated many theories and approaches to cater to ESL learners writing needs. These writing approaches has gone through a lot of changes over the years to enable the second language learners to become a good writer. A few approaches identified by practitioners for ESL learners they are such as product, process, genre approach and process genre approach. Product based Approaches Product based approach denotes a writing process which aims to see the end product. Regularly, students imitate a model text to produce one. In other words, students mimic a model composition provided by the teachers. For instance, in the writing classrooms, teachers provide examples or model composition for the students and based on the models, students produce a similar composition. Product based approach lost its popularity as it has no concern over the process of the writing but the grammar structure and syntax. It demotivates the students when accuracy in mimicking is focused rather than students' creativity Process based Approach On the other hand, process-based approach gives great importance to the process of getting the end product.

There are four processes involved in the writing process; planning, drafting, revising and editing. Kroll (2001, p.221) "explains drafting and receiving feedback on their drafts, be it from peers and/or from the teacher, followed by revision of their evolving texts is one of the crucial steps in the process-based approach"[2]. Adopting this approach enable writers to move back and forth to improve their writing. It also promotes creativity when the writers create their own composition. Thus, it is seen as a dynamic approach as recursive process takes place. Process approach is popular due to its benefits. Students can enhance their writing abilities in the classroom as scaffolding occurs. Other than that, feedback is given by teachers and peer, so it gives opportunity for students to become a better writer. According to Maarof et al. (2011, p.30) "teacher feedback is regarded as a main requirement for improvement in students' essay writing". In addition, it stresses on thinking process, this will promote creativity[3].

Despite all the advantages, process-based approach has it disadvantages, it consumes a lot of time, focuses on the process instead of structures and grammar. Genre based Approach In

contrast, genre approach looks “writing as pre-dominantly linguistic but, emphasize that writing varies with the social context in which it is produced producing texts based on social context”[4]. Genre based approach give importance to various types of writing and text types and intertwined with social needs. It has some advantages as such as students learns variety of sentence structures for different text types.

Currently, process writing is given much emphasizes in ESL classrooms. It helps students to produce and kinds of writing by employing the four steps. Besides employing these approaches, teachers also employ different types of strategies to make the teaching and learning writing in second language classroom in fruitful. Some of the popular strategies “include modelling, shared writing, guided writing, and interactive writing”. This approach has its plus points, that is, it is more suitable to students in secondary schools. Its limitations are, it needs careful and tedious planning, it consumes a lot of time in planning and teaching. Process Product Approach Process product approach combines product approach and process approach. Employing this approach is to develop students writing skills by mastering product approach prior to process approach. Students need to master writing mechanics and get familiar with sample texts or model essays at this stage and proceed with process writing, which is developing writing employing all the stages in process writing stages namely, prewriting, drafting, revising, editing and publishing to compose a own generated story. This approach's main disadvantages are linked to its complexity and the time and cost engaged in achieving it.

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that ESL teachers are is best to employ process based approach, especially in teaching of secondary level and tertiary level education. Undoubtedly true, adult students are more independent and they possess sufficient knowledge in content and their language mastery is greater than the younger ESL learner as they are novice writers. Due, to these advantages possessed by adult learners, it will be undemanding for these learners to employ the writing process systematically. Finding supports these ideas, as most of the studies selected process-based approach studies which are done towards university participants. Thus, to scaffold the teaching of writing in higher education level, process writing will be the best approach. Meanwhile, in secondary and primary school level, process-product approach and process-genre approach will be suitable to be employed in the ESL classrooms, as scaffolding is given importance when selecting these approaches. Younger students need scaffolding in order to produce a good writing.

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